

Evaluation of the effectiveness of the use of games in the teaching of Production Engineering: an experiment with Goldratt Simulator

Bárbara Yumi Hotta¹, Fernando Bernardi de Souza¹, Bruna Andrade Machado¹, José de Souza Rodrigues¹

¹ Production Engineering Department, Faculty of Engineering, UNESP, Bauru, São Paulo, Brazil

Email: barbara.hotta@hotmail.com, fbernardi@unesp.br, bruna.a.machado@unesp.br, jsrod@feb.unesp.br

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Abstract

Traditional and theoretical classes are usually tiring and their contents are poorly absorbed. One way to apply and fix the contents in a more attractive and motivating way is through the use of active methodologies, whose use has been encouraged by the new curricular guidelines of engineering courses in Brazil. Game-based learning (GBL) is one of such approach. Although many games are already used in classroom environments, e.g. Beer Game, Lean Board Game and Goldratt Simulator, there is still a lack of studies on the effectiveness of its application. In 2020, a study about the use of games in Production Engineering courses was initiated, which resulted in the development of questionnaires and the suggestion of a methodology for evaluating the effectiveness of the use of GBL. In order to identify the effectiveness of the use of Goldratt Simulator, as a game, in the learning process this evaluation methodology was applied during an experiment carried out in the discipline of Production Management IV, in which two groups were defined (control and experimental). After the classes and the application of the questionnaires, it became evident: greater engagement and confidence by the experimental group and greater fixation of concepts by the control group. Furthermore, the evaluative tools proved to be adequate to give feedback to the teacher, presenting themselves as an important diagnostic tool.

Keywords: Learning evaluation methodology; GBL; Educational games; Production engineering.

1 Introduction

Changes in student profiles, who think that theoretical and traditional classes are usually tiring and demotivating, have led to new teaching methodologies being developed and applied (Rubeus, 2021).

The use of such methodologies has even been encouraged by teaching guidelines, which suggest that active methodologies (in which students become protagonists in the learning process) are constantly used (MEC, 2019).

One of the methodologies that promises to stimulate student development is Game Based Learning (GBL), which uses analogue or digital games in classrooms (Karagioras & Niemann, 2017). The methodology is mainly used to generate greater engagement, motivate action, promote learning and solve problems in a creative way (Lester, 2014). It is an excellent way to help students lose resistance in the face of complex topics (Sales et al., 2017).

There are several studies that present the creation of game-based learning environments for a wide range of curricula (Warren et al., 2008; Kebritchi & Hirumi, 2010). In the university where this project has been developed, some analogue games are already used, such as Beer Game and Lean Board Game, and virtual simulators, such as Goldratt Simulator, to support the Production Management disciplines of the Production Engineering course. It so happens that, so far, in the course in question, this methodology has been applied without carrying out a scientific evaluation of the benefits of its use.

According to Lester (2014), research on game-based learning has matured and today there are empirical studies that qualitatively demonstrate students' learning gains when interacting with educational games in a variety of subjects, however, these studies often make use of non-standard instruments. Furthermore, quantitative research is more difficult to identify.

In 2021 a research developed by the authors resulted in the elaboration of a set of tools (questionnaire to characterise the participants and three instruments evaluation) that allow to analyse the perception of students and the level of learning obtained by the use of games in the learning process (Machado et al., 2021). During

the same period, the Goldratt Simulator was used as a game in the discipline of Production Management IV, offered to a 4th year class at a Brazilian public university. Due to the importance of analysing the effectiveness of its application, the authors of this research used the tools previously developed in an attempt to answer the following question: is the use of Goldratt Simulator effective for greater student motivation and learning?

In order to verify the effectiveness of the use of the Goldratt Simulator as a motivation and learning tool, a research was conducted applying the tools previously developed. The instruments and results are presented in this work.

2 Methods

After carrying out a systematic review to identify instruments for evaluating the effectiveness of the use of games in teaching, the results of which were published by Machado et al. (2021), an action research was carried out regarding the application of a game already consolidated and commonly applied in the discipline of Production Management IV of the course studied, which uses the Goldratt Simulator, a simulator of the production process, which allows the player to identify and deal with problems that can occur in real situations and that allows the learning of several concepts of Theory of Constraints, an important content for the Production Engineering course.

According to Oquisit (1978, apud Mello et al, 2012), action research can be defined as the production of knowledge guided by practice, occurring simultaneously to the modification of a reality that is also part of the research process. Thiollent (2007, apud Mello et al, 2012) emphasises that for a research to be considered an action research, it is essential that there is an action on the part of the people involved in the problem under observation, that this action is non-trivial to the point of needing to investigation and that researchers play an active role in conducting, monitoring and evaluating the research. It is added that this method is appropriate when the research question is used to clarify how an action of a person can improve the functioning of the system and how this process will take place, thus aiming to learn from it (Coghlan & Brannick, 2008). apud Mello et al, 2012).

Thus, an experiment was carried out in the discipline of Production Management IV of the Production Engineering course of a Brazilian public institution. In this experiment, the class was divided into two groups, one group was exposed to a theoretical-expository teaching-learning process, while the other used an approach along the lines of GBL (Game-based learning). With the purpose of measuring the effectiveness of each approach, the students of each group were questioned using the evaluation tools developed from the bibliographic research.

At this stage, of the 32 students in the class, 15 volunteered to participate in the research, the participants were divided between the control (9 students) and experimental (6 students) groups in order to maintain a certain homogeneity in relation to the average of ages and gender. However, right at the beginning of the questionnaires, 5 students in the control group dropped out, leaving 10 participants.

3 Evaluation methodologies

In view of the existence of few validation studies on the effectiveness of the use of games in teaching, the authors of this work carried out, between the years 2020 and 2021, a research whose result was the elaboration of a questionnaire to characterise the participants and three instruments evaluation, one of perception, another of self-evaluation and a third of learning. These three instruments were published in the proceedings of PAEE/ALE'2021 under the title "Game-based learning in a Production Engineering course in Brazil." by Machado et al. (2021) and are the basis of this research, since they were used to measure the effects of applying the Goldratt Simulator in the discipline of Production Management IV. The instruments created and used throughout this new research are presented below.

3.1 Participant's characterization questionnaire

The participants' characterization questionnaire begins with the student's acceptance to participate in the experiment and is applied through "Google Forms". The questionnaire comprises the following questions:

Gender: () Female () Male () Not informed
Age: _____
What is your level of knowledge about Theory of Constraints (TOC)?
 () I've never heard of it, I don't know what it is
 () I've heard of it, but I don't know what it is
 () I've heard of it and I know it's related to production systems
 () I have read and / or attended classes on the subject
 () I know and am able to discuss the matter properly
Based on the teaching plan presented for the subject, analyse the following statements using the Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree):
 I believe that subject is important for my training
 I would enrol in the course if it was not mandatory
 I think the proposed assessment is fair
 I think the proposed assessment is challenging
 I think the proposed methodology looks interesting

* Main concept subject to be worked on in the experiment

Figure 1. Specific participant's characterization questionnaire

Source: Machado et al (2021)

This questionnaire must be applied at the beginning of the classes, before the first instructions on the content are offered, so that the groups can be properly organised.

3.2 Perception questionnaire

Perception analyses reach the first two levels proposed by Kirkpatrick (reaction and learning). The first analysis will begin with the application of a perception questionnaire combined with the Flow Theory.

Using the Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), students from both groups should answer the following questions:

Absorption / Immersion:
 1. During the activity I lost track of time
 2. During the activity, I felt totally immersed
 3. The activity made me excited
 4. The activity made me feel self-confident
 5. The activity stimulated my interest
 6. The activity piqued my curiosity

Pleasure:
 7. The activity gave me a good feeling
 8. I had fun during the activity
 9. The activity brought me joy
 10. The activity was pleasant

Motivation:
 11. This type of activity should be carried out more frequently
 12. This is an activity that I willingly performed
 13. This is an activity that I would participate in even if it was not linked to the presence
 14. This is an activity that I would participate in even if it was not linked to the note
 15. This is an activity that I would do even though I didn't receive anything in return

Skills:
 16. This activity improved my critical thinking
 17. This activity improved my problem-solving ability
 18. This activity improved my analytical ability
 19. This activity improved my ability to manage time and resources
 20. Some problems became clear with this activity

Figure 2. A generic developed perception questionnaire

Source: Machado et al (2021)

3.3 Post-test

After conducting the experiment, the following questionnaire must be applied to students in both groups. For a coherent evaluation it is fundamental that the questions are neutral, that is, they are not directly related to the game. We understand that the ideal would be the realisation of conceptual questions that could be analysed in a practical way, for example by a TRUE or FALSE model.

Mark the sentences below with TRUE or FALSE:

1. The Theory of Constraints (TOC) argues that companies have many constraints that make it difficult to reach their goal
2. The Theory of Constraints (TOC) states that local optima result in global optima
3. Capacity constrained resources (RRC) are resources that, if poorly managed, can become bottlenecks
4. Bottlenecks impede demands from being fully met
5. Bottlenecks and RRCs are synonymous
6. The buffer is the stock of materials in process that must be present throughout the entire production line
7. The Rope is the sequencing of material release to the factory based on the discounted Lung Drum
8. The production schedule of the Bottleneck is the Drum and it is from there that the rest of the factory must be subordinated
9. An hour lost on a non-bottleneck resource is an hour lost on the entire system
10. An hour saved on a non-bottleneck resource is an hour gained system-wide
11. In the classic Drum-Lung-Rope method, in-process buffers are dimensioned and controlled in the form of time
12. Non-bottleneck resources should adjust their production speeds to the Drum

Figure 3. The post-test with specific questions about Theory of Constraints

Source: Adapted from Machado et al (2021)

3.4 Self-assessment questionnaire

As a last tool, a self-assessment is suggested. In this, students will have the chance to review the contents worked and analyse their own level of understanding.

Analyse your level of understanding by checking 1 (I didn't understand) to 5 (I fully understood).

1. The Theory of Constraints (TOC) argues that companies have very FEW constraints that limit the achievement of the goal
2. The Theory of Constraints (TOC) states that local optima DO NOT result in global optima
3. Capacity constrained resources (RRC) are resources that, if poorly managed, can become bottlenecks
4. Bottlenecks impede demands from being fully met
5. Bottlenecks and RRCs are NOT synonymous
6. Time buffers are reflected in physical inventories located at strategic points to protect system constraints
7. The Rope is the sequencing of material release to the factory based on the Drum discounted the Buffer
8. The production schedule of the Bottleneck is the Drum and it is from there that the rest of the factory must be subordinated
9. An hour lost on a NON-bottleneck resource is NOT a system-wide lost hour, but an hour lost on the bottleneck resource is a system-wide lost hour
10. An hour saved on a NON-bottleneck resource is NOT an hour gained system-wide.
11. In the classic Drum-Buffer-Rope method, in-process buffers are dimensioned and controlled in the form of time
12. Non-bottleneck resources must NOT adjust their production speeds to the Drum. They must operate according to roadrunner logic

Figure 4. The self-assessment with specific affirmatives about Theory of Constraints

Source: Adapted from Machado et al (2021)

4 Results

As for the application of the Goldratt Simulator, the 10 students who participated answered the questionnaires to characterize the participants and the perception and learning assessment questionnaires, but only 9 responded to the self-assessment.

4.1 Participant's characterization questionnaire

Regarding gender, 5 men and 5 women participated in the experiment. The average age is 22.8 years old, with a maximum age of 27 and a minimum age of 21. Regarding the level of knowledge of the Theory of Constraints, all 10 participants already knew something about the subject. For questions related to expectations of the topic discussed in the course, the means and deviations were presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Assessment of participants' expectations

	Average	σ
I believe that this subject is important for my training	4.8	0.6
I would enrol in the course if it was not mandatory	4.0	1.1
I think the proposed assessment is fair	4.4	0.7
I think the proposed assessment is challenging	4.3	0.7
I think the proposed methodology looks interesting	4.4	0.8

Source: authors (2021)

4.2 Perception questionnaire

In the perception assessment, composed of 20 questions whose answers were based on a Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), the means and deviations between the control and experimental groups were calculated and are shown in Tables 2, 3, 4 and 5.

Table 2: Participants' perception of Absorption / Immersion

	Control Group		Experimental Group	
	Average	σ	Average	σ
Q1. During the activity I lost track of time	1.8	0.5	4.2	0.4
Q2. During the activity, I felt totally immersed	2.8	1.5	4.5	0.5
Q3. The activity made me excited	2.8	1.5	3.7	0.8
Q4. The activity made me feel self-confident	3.3	1.5	4.5	0.5
Q5. The activity stimulated my interest	3.8	1.5	4.8	0.4
Q6. The activity piqued my curiosity	3.8	1.5	4.8	0.4

Source: authors (2021)

Regarding immersion, it was noted that the experimental group felt more immersed and motivated, presenting higher averages and smaller deviations. Attention to the first item, that refers to the loss of the notion of time, whose difference between the groups is quite significant, corroborating the idea that traditional classes are more tiring. This statement is also confirmed by the report of one of the participants:

"As a member of the control group, I believe it is worth highlighting the teacher's didactic ability. In the content presented, the examples used, clarity in speech and attention to students' doubts count a lot for a very positive evaluation of the activity taught. Without these highlighted points, due to the relatively long class time (4h), I don't think I would feel involved and excited to make the most of it. As classes are usually long, they can become tiring and even though there is a good effort from the teacher and an effort on the part of the students, even so, with only theoretical classes it is more difficult to maintain concentration at all times and lose this notion. of time. By adding a more dynamic activity, students are more involved and time goes faster".

Table 3: Participants' perception of Pleasure

	Control Group		Experimental Group	
	Average	σ	Average	σ
Q7. The activity gave me a good feeling	3.8	1.5	4.5	0.8
Q8. I had fun during the activity	2.8	1.0	4.8	0.4
Q9. The activity brought me joy	2.8	1.0	4.0	1.1
Q10. The activity was pleasant	3.3	1.5	4.5	0.5

Source: authors (2021)

For pleasure, the experimental group also presented higher ratings, with attention to item Q9 in which the deviation of the experimental group exceeded the control group, even though the average is higher.

Table 4: Participants' perception of Motivation

	Control Group		Experimental Group	
	Average	σ	Average	σ
Q11. This type of activity should be carried out more frequently	3.3	1.0	4.8	0.4
Q12. This is an activity that I willingly performed	4.0	1.4	4.8	0.4
Q13. This is an activity that I would participate in even if it was not linked to the presence	3.8	1.5	4.3	0.8
Q14. This is an activity that I would participate in even if it was not linked to the note	3.8	1.5	4.5	0.8
Q15. This is an activity that I would do even though I didn't receive anything in return	3.8	1.5	4.3	0.8

Source: authors (2021)

As for motivation, again, the experimental group showed higher ratings, with lower deviations than the control group.

Table 5: Participants' perception of improved Skills

	Control Group		Experimental Group	
	Average	σ	Average	σ
Q16. This activity improved my critical thinking	3.8	1.5	4.8	0.4
Q17. This activity improved my problem-solving ability	3.5	1.3	4.5	0.5
Q18. This activity improved my analytical ability	3.5	1.3	4.5	0.8
Q19. This activity improved my ability to manage time and resources	3.0	1.4	4.5	0.5
Q20. Some problems became clear with this activity	2.5	1.3	4.8	0.4

Source: authors (2021)

Regarding skills, the control group presented lower averages with always higher deviations than the experimental group.

Thus, it can be seen that the experimental group has a higher average for all questions. This shows that, in general, the group that used the game became more immersed, had more pleasure in performing the activity, felt more motivated and believed to have improved their skills.

4.3 Post-test

For the second instrument, the learning assessment, made up of 12 True/False questions, a different result was obtained than expected. The control group had a higher average of correct answers than the experimental group, as shown in Table 6. This can be explained by reasons such as incorrect division of groups, greater ease on the part of students who belonged to the control group or lack of attention to answer the questionnaire. A new application, with a larger sample of people, may indicate a different average, since the sample was composed of the most engaged students in the class.

Another factor that may have been a complicating factor for the learning of the experimental group is that the interest in simulating the activity and the fact that the students were in environments different from the teacher (since the classes were held remotely due to the pandemic) prevented the better control of the teacher and allowed the students to simulate while the teacher performed the explanations, which are of paramount importance for obtaining the concepts presented.

Table 6: Average of correct answers in the learning evaluation form by group

Group	Average
Control Group	9.25
Experimental Group	8.00

Source: authors (2021)

A feedback was received on this form:

I found the insights obtained by using the game helped me a lot to understand. Anyway, I think the 4 hours were a bit exhausting and may have hampered learning.

This report brings a reflection: even though the use of the game makes the class "lighter", as observed by the first evaluation instrument, time is still a critical point.

It is also worth mentioning that questions 1, 6 and 12 were the ones with the highest frequency of errors, with only 4, 4 and 2 correct answers respectively.

4.4 Self-assessment questionnaire

The self-assessment added to the results of the learning assessment (post-test) serves as a parameter for the teacher to identify the points of difficulty for students to understand. Thus, following the Likert scale pattern 1 (I did not understand at all) to 5 (I fully understood), the following averages were obtained for the established statements (Table 7).

Table 7: Average of self-assessment questions per group.

Group	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	Q10	Q11	Q12	Total
Control Group	3.75	3.5	4.75	4	4,5	5	4.5	3.75	5	4.75	5	3.75	4.35
Experimental Group	3.6	4.8	4.6	4.8	4.2	4	4.6	4.8	4.4	4.2	4.4	4	4.37

Source: authors (2021).

In general, a high level of confidence and security in the answers by all students can be observed. An interesting detail is that the lowest averages of the experimental group are really related to the questions whose students had greater assimilation difficulties (1, 6 and 12), according to the number of errors in the learning assessment.

5 Conclusion

Following the idea defended by McGonigall (2011 apud Moores, 2016) that participation in games should be voluntary, participation in the experiment was optional, which implied a low adherence of students. The

exceptions refer to students who normally interact more with the teacher and are more willing to participate in classes. The division of experimental and control groups in an entire room could indicate other results, especially in the learning assessment instrument. It is also necessary to think that in this freedom of participation, those who chose not to take part in the research, even because they had never used a game as a teaching tool, may have missed the opportunity to discover a new method in which they could enjoy more, have identification with and ease to learn.

The perception assessment instrument showed an acceptance of the use of games, as well as greater immersion, pleasure, motivation and skills improvement perception on the part of those who participated. It also indicated greater development of important and expected skills of a production engineer. Participants were very interested in the proposal to use these means as a form of teaching. The students did not present technical difficulties to answer the questionnaires. The use of games and simple assessment tools, such as those developed in this study, are alternatives to measure student performance and perceive difficult points, without having the pressure of a test, in addition to returning the results more quickly to students.

The learning assessment brought attention for pointing out a different result than expected. Students who did not use the simulator performed better, even though they had less confidence in their answers, as indicated by the self-assessment form. It is important that there are new applications with a greater number of students to verify if the results are maintained in this proportion.

In order to answer the question of this work, by a perception way, the use of the game brings more immersion, pleasure, motivation and skills improvement. Although, in the learning field, the result has shown to be inferior to those who used the game. This may be due to the fact that the application was carried out online (not face-to-face), with the teacher not having control over the students regarding the fact that they stopped using the simulator so that they could focus attention on the explanations, which were essential for the correct absorption of the concepts that were collected during the post-test. The results presented by the post-test and the self-assessment questionnaire were quite consistent and corroborate the evidence of the quality of the instruments used.

For future research, the application with a larger number of participants is indicated and the need to investigate the low adherence of students to the research is evidenced, since a lack of time for extra activities was justified, even when the application was made during the class schedule and questionnaires take very few minutes to be answered. It is also worth mentioning the opportunity to apply the assessment instruments to other subjects and even other teaching areas, with the necessary adaptations.

6 References

- Karagiorgas, D. N., & Niemann, S. (2017). Gamification and game-based learning. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 45(4), 499-519.
- Kebritchi, M., Hirumi, A., & Bai, H. (2010). The effects of modern mathematics computer games on mathematics achievement and class motivation. *Computers & education*, 55(2), 427-443.
- Lester, J. C., Spires, H. A., Nietfeld, J. L., Minogue, J., Mott, B. W., & Lobene, E. V. (2014). Designing game-based learning environments for elementary science education: A narrative-centered learning perspective. *Information Sciences*, 264, 4-18.
- Machado, B. A., de Souza, F. B., Rodrigues, J. De S. & Hotta, B. Y. (2021). Game-based learning in a Production Engineering course in Brazil. In: *Proceedings of the International Conference on Active Learning in Engineering Education. PAEE/ALE 2021*, 7 - 9 July 2021. Braga - Portugal. (Conference website).
- MEC – Ministério da Educação (2019). Diretrizes Curriculares Nacionais. Resolução n. 2, de 24 de abril de 2019.
- Mello, C. H. P., Turrioni, J. B., Xavier, A. F., & Campos, D. F. (2012). Pesquisa-ação na engenharia de produção: proposta de estruturação para sua condução. *Production*, 22, 1-13.
- Moores, T. T. (2016). Teaching Tip: An Introduction to the Business Game 'Flowers for the World'. *Journal of Information Systems Education*, 27(4), 217.
- Rubeus. (2021). O novo perfil dos alunos: 5 comportamentos que sua IE precisa conhecer! [Post da web]. Recuperado de <https://rubeus.com.br/blog/o-novo-perfil-dos-alunos/>
- Sales, G. L., Cunha, J. L. L., Gonçalves, A. J., da Silva, J. B., & dos Santos, R. L. (2017). Gamificação e ensinagem híbrida na sala de aula de física: metodologias ativas aplicadas aos espaços de aprendizagem e na prática docente. *Conexões-Ciência e Tecnologia*, 11(2), 45-52.
- Warren, S. J., Dondlinger, M. J., & Barab, S. A. (2008). A MUVE towards PBL writing: Effects of a digital learning environment designed to improve elementary student writing. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 41(1), 113-140.